

ON THE ROLE OF MATRIX NONLINEARITY IN MECHANICAL MODELING OF LONG-FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Context

Long-fiber reinforced composites with thermosetting matrices are the most frequently used composite type for high performance applications, such as in the aerospace industry. In recent years, complex fiber architectures, such as 3D weaving or braiding, have become more and more common due to their high flexibility to form complex shapes and good resistance to impact and delamination [1]. The structural performance of these composites depends on a multitude of aspects, including choice of the constituents, fiber arrangement, and manufacturing process conditions. In order to produce really competitive composite structures, all these aspects have to be taken into account in the design process.

To this aim, a modeling chain is assembled, linking manufacturing process to multi-scale mechanical modeling. Composites with woven reinforcements have three characteristic scales: micro- (of the fiber), meso- (of the yarn), and macro-scale (of the structure). The manufacturing process plays an important role at all these scales, among which micro- and meso-scale are particularly interesting: the micro-scale, because the constituents can be treated separately, which is important in order to take into account the influence of the manufacturing process, and the meso-scale, at which the reinforcement architecture is represented.

The cure cycle of a thermosetting matrix has an important impact on its mechanical properties, in particular on nonlinear phenomena, such as viscoplasticity. The topic of this contribution is the influence of such nonlinearities on the mechanical performance of the composite. Since nonlinear behavior is mostly due to the matrix and the fiber-matrix interface, it is clearly based upon microscopic mechanisms. We therefore focus here on the micro-scale, and study the influence of matrix nonlinearity on the behavior at the next superior scale. Material

anisotropy, matrix damage, and fiber-matrix decohesion are also taken into account. The influence of the cure cycle on the composite part can then be analyzed, in order to optimize its properties by adjusting the cure process.

A yarn in a long-fiber woven reinforcement consists of locally almost parallel fibers. It can therefore be treated in a good approximation as a composite with a unidirectional (UD) fiber orientation, as those used in composite laminates. Over the last decade, within the framework of a world wide failure exercise (WWFE) [2-4], the most common models of failure of composite laminates have been compared. Some of the models give excellent predictions [5], and in most cases, the model parameters can be identified by means of macro-scale experiments on the laminates. The disadvantage is that there is no direct link to the properties of the constituents. Hence, the model parameters have to be re-identified, each time the manufacturing process is changed, leading to high experimental costs of composite optimization. A reliable multi-scale modeling chain starting from the micro-scale and taking into account the manufacturing process would therefore be of great benefit for the industrial designer. It will be shown in the following sections, that in order to obtain the experimentally observed failure curve at the ply (or yarn) scale, it is of fundamental importance to correctly model the properties of the constituents at the micro-scale.

2 Calculation of transverse composite strength

On the one hand, ply strength under combined loadings (tension or compression and shear) in the plane perpendicular to the fiber direction are more difficult to measure than in direction of the fibers. On the other hand, in laminates and even more frequently in composites with woven reinforce-

ments, the first damage usually occurs in a ply or a yarn that is oriented transversely to the loading direction [6]. These load cases are therefore particularly interesting for numerical simulation. In order to determine the failure curve in the transverse plane, we increase proportionally the average strain in a representative micro-scale volume element (RVE). Failure is reached when the maximum (or minimum in the case of compression) principal stress attains its absolute maximum over the loading curve. The stress locus corresponds to a point on the failure curve. This method has been widely used in the literature [7-10].

The choice of the RVE is crucial [8,9], as the obtained failure stress strongly depends on the fiber distribution [11], which is approximately random [12]. Nevertheless, periodic fiber distributions are often used for simplicity [7,10]. Fig. 1 shows the failures curve obtained for different RVEs under different combinations of transverse tension and compression with in-plane shear. The RVE containing only one fiber corresponds to a periodic hexagonal fiber distribution. The other two RVEs are periodically repeated random distributions of 10 and 30 fibers. Periodic boundary conditions are applied in each case. The results show that there is no significant difference between the cases of 10 and 30 fibers. We also see that the results do not agree with experimental observations for a UD ply made of T300 carbon fibers with LY566 epoxy matrix [13], except for the case of pure tension in the periodic fiber distribution. This corresponds to the observations of Zhao et al. [7].

Fig.1. Calculated failure stresses of RVEs with different numbers of fibers (Nf), compared to experimentally observed ply strengths [13].

The fiber is assumed to be linearly elastic with transversely isotropic properties. Fiber damage is not taken into account in the simulations presented here, since under transverse loading, damage in the composite occurs within the matrix and at the interface between fiber and matrix. The latter is modeled by a cohesive zone approach with “plastic decohesion” [14], in order to take into account friction effects at the interface under compressive loadings. The results in Fig. 1 have been obtained using an elastic damage model for the matrix: Isotropic linear elastic behavior is assumed up to a certain stress level. From that point on, stiffness is rapidly reduced with growing strain. The stiffness reduction is continuous to ensure numerical stability. However, it is sufficiently steep, such as to reproduce brittle failure. An isotropic damage model is used here for simplicity.

The elastic properties of the fibers are reasonably well known [15]. For the matrix, we used the failure stresses (80 MPa under tension and 120 MPa under compression) obtained from experimental test on macro-scale pure matrix specimens [15]. The interface properties are difficult to measure directly in-situ and are therefore adjusted to obtain the best possible approximation to the experimental data. Since the calculated failure stresses are far below the experimental values for almost any load case, we set the interface strength to infinity in Fig. 1, which is equivalent to not using a cohesive zone model between fibers and matrix. A weaker interface would only reduce strength, so that this case represents the best possible fit for the given matrix and fiber properties. The results clearly show that macro-scale matrix strengths cannot be used for micro-scale modeling (cf. section 3).

In the literature, two models are most commonly used for the matrix: an elastic damage model [7,10] and an elastic-plastic model [9]. The first (used in Fig. 1) corresponds to a brittle, the second to a ductile material. We will study in the following the influence of these properties on the composite failure curves.

3 Microscale matrix behavior

Macro-scale specimens of thermosetting matrices usually exhibit an elastic, brittle behavior. Damage and failure is dominated by defects such as surface

flaws or embedded particles [16,17]. In a micro-scale matrix volume within a composite, surface flaws do not play a role, and the influence of defects is strongly reduced due to size effects. Accordingly, microscopic matrix strength is significantly higher in all load directions [17]. Adjusting the matrix strength for these size effects, compressive and tensile transverse strength of the UD ply can be reproduced (blue curve in Fig. 2). However, the predicted in-plane shear strength, in particular if combined with transverse compression, remains far below the experimentally observed values.

While failure under compression remains matrix controlled, under tension the fiber-matrix interface becomes dominant. In fact, in order to correctly reproduce both tensile and compressive ply strength, the interface must be weaker than the matrix. This corresponds to what is usually is the case in carbon-epoxy composites [18]. However, if macro-scale matrix properties are used, a weaker interface would create even stronger discrepancies with respect to the experimental data.

In the case of pure tension, there are thus two sources of errors, which may compensate each other, due to their opposite effect. The use of a periodic fiber distribution overestimates [11] and the use of macroscopic matrix properties underestimates transverse tensile strength. The fact that shear and compressive strength are not reproduced using the same approach, and the cited studies prove that fiber distribution and size effect have both to be taken into account in micro-scale modeling of composites.

Fig.2. Comparison between failure stresses under transverse tension and compression combined with in-of-plane shear, obtained with the elastic (blue) and the viscoplastic (red) matrix damage model.

While matrix failure remains brittle under tension even at the micro-scale, under compression and shear the matrix undergoes considerable plastic deformation before failure [17,19]. Typically, after an initial linear elastic stage, a yield peak is reached, which is followed by a transitory softening phase. At large strains, hardening due to stretching of the polymer chains becomes dominant, and failure occurs at a stress superior to the yield peak stress [19].

This behavior is modeled using a standard approach for isotropic viscoplastic materials [e.g., 20]. A von Mises yield criterion is used to compute the overstress. Norton's flow rule [20] relates the overstress to the rate of equivalent plastic flow. The transitory yield peak is reproduced by an isotropic softening rule with a saturation value, in order to ensure the convexity of the yield surface. The effect of polymer chain stretching is simulated by nonlinear kinematic hardening. Flow, softening, and hardening rules have been chosen as simple as possible, but such that they reproduce the characteristic effects of a polymer under compression and shear. Damage is modeled (as in the brittle model) by a rapid reduction of stiffness, once the damage criterion has been exceeded. However, in the viscoplastic model, we distinguish between damage due to crazing, which is guided by the maximum principle tensile stress [17], and damage due to chain rupture, which occurs during the hardening phase, after yielding. The latter is therefore guided by the von Mises equivalent of the kinematic hardening variable, which is directly related to the polymer chain stretching.

Fig.3. Brittle (blue) and viscoplastic damageable (red) matrix behavior under uniaxial tension.

Fig.4. Brittle (blue) and viscoplastic damageable (red) matrix behavior under uniaxial compression.

Figs. 3 and 4 show the matrix behavior obtained with both the brittle and the viscoplastic damage model under pure tension and compression. While the tensile behavior only changes in the almost totally damaged state due to different formulations of the models, the compressive behavior changes drastically due to the presence of yield.

4 Discussion of the results

In Fig. 2 we compare the failure curves obtained with the matrix models shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Under pure tension and pure compression the failure stress remains almost unchanged. However, in the whole shear part of the failure curve, the calculated strengths are considerably higher than in the case of a brittle matrix model. Moreover, the shape of the experimentally observed failure curve is very well reproduced.

The quality of reproduction is of course due to the fact that the matrix properties have been adjusted such as to yield the best fitting failure curve. However, even though the viscoplastic matrix behavior is much more complex than the elastic brittle behavior, only few parameters have a significant influence on the failure curve.

First, we have to note that the tensile matrix strength and the normal interface strength have not been changed with respect to the brittle model. In fact, failure under transverse tension is dominated by mode I fiber-matrix decohesion in both cases, hence the normal interface strength must be the same. Furthermore, compressive and shear yield strength

in the viscoplastic model have been chosen equal to the compressive and shear matrix strength of the brittle model that reproduced correctly the transverse compressive ply strength. Finally, the failure curve obtained with the viscoplastic matrix model is surprisingly independent of the final compressive and shear failure stresses of the matrix after yield.

The most important parameters of the matrix model are thus its yield strengths (which, however, have been set equal to the strengths used in the brittle matrix model) and the mode II fiber-matrix interface properties. In fact, the in-plane shear strength of the ply depends significantly on the mode II interface strength. In the case of a brittle matrix model, this property also had an influence on the in-plane shear ply strength, but even increasing mode II strength and tenacity and interface friction to unreasonably high values did not allow for a correct reproduction of the experimental values.

All these observations show that it is of fundamental importance to take into account matrix nonlinearity at the micro-scale if meso-scale strengths should be predicted from micro-scale simulations. Correct micro-scale modeling is also important to predict failure stresses under complex load cases, which cannot easily be studied experimentally (for example triaxial loadings, or out-of-plane shear deformations).

In Fig. 5 we show the failure curves for transverse tension and compression combined with out-of-plane shear stress, obtained with both matrix models. Out-of-plane shear strength is particularly difficult

Fig.5. Comparison between failure stresses under transverse tension and compression combined with out-of-plane shear, obtained with the elastic (blue) and the viscoplastic (red) matrix damage model.

to measure experimentally, and to our knowledge, there is almost no data available in the literature. However, under flexural loading of structural composite elements, out-of-plane shear may be an important cause of failure.

The results indicate that for out-of-plane shear the influence of matrix yielding is much less important than for in-plane shear. Nevertheless, there are differences under combined compression and shear, which is where matrix yielding dominates over crazing and fiber-matrix decohesion.

5 Conclusions

Damage evolution and failure in a composite section with locally parallel fibers has been modeled at the micro-scale, at which fibers and matrix can be treated separately. Using an elastic damage model for the matrix with strength parameters identified from macro-scale experiments it is not possible to reproduce experimentally observed failure stresses under transverse tension and compression combined with in-plane shear stress. If the correct fiber distribution (locally random) is taken into account, the differences are even more significant.

Two reasons have been identified for these discrepancies. First, due to size effects and the absence of surface flaws, the local in-situ strength of matrix volumes within the composite is significantly higher than that observed on macro-scale bulk specimens. Second, due to the same effects, under compression and shear the matrix undergoes significant plastic deformation before failure, even though its macro-scale behavior is apparently brittle for all load cases. In fact, apparently brittle failure at the macro-scale does not exclude the presence of important plastic strain at the micro-scale, if the latter is highly localized. The contribution of such localized yield to the macro-scopic deformation is indeed negligible. However, its influence on onset and evolution of damage, a very local process, cannot be neglected.

The effect of matrix yield is particularly important under in-plane shear stress. For accurate prediction of transverse tensile and compressive strength, it is sufficient to use the correct micro-scale in-situ matrix strength.

In order to predict meso-scale damage criteria (for example for a UD-ply in a laminate or for a yarn in a

composite with woven reinforcements) from micro-scale simulations, it is not sufficient to only carry out tests on macro-scale specimens to identify the properties of the constituents. Micro-scale properties are needed, which cannot be directly inferred from macro-scale test data. They have to be identified either directly from micro-scale tests or indirectly by fitting test data of the superior scales, as done in the present work. Since micro-scale tests are often complicated and it is difficult to measure in-situ properties of the constituents in a composite separately (in particular the properties of the fiber-matrix interface), the latter method often is the only possible one.

The interest of using micro-scale modeling to derive meso-scale damage criteria instead of identifying them directly from meso-scale tests lies in the optimization of the composite material. In fact, the effect of a variation of a constituent property or of the manufacturing process can only be determined by either a very large number of experiments, or by multi-scale modeling of the manufacturing process and the mechanics of the composite, from the scale of the constituents to the structure.

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